

Hf-Nd isotope study of Archean granitoids and implication for mineralization

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Zircon grains from granitoid samples from different blocks of the Archean Karelian craton have been studied for their Lu-Hf isotope composition. These new results are combined with previously published bulk-rock Sm-Nd isotopes to constrain the crustal architecture and evolution of the Karelian craton, as well their links to mineralization associated with different types of mineral systems.

Introduction

The development of the Mineral Systems Approach (MSA) considering fundamental source-pathway-sink processes has been a major tool to identify regions of high exploration potential. Knowledge of the large-scale crustal evolution is crucial to define the crustal architecture, and the localisation of mineralization. Regional scale geophysics may provide direct information on the present-day lithospheric structure [1]. However, multiple-stage tectonic events may have modified the paleo-structures. The Sm-Nd and Lu-Hf isotopic systematics have previously been applied to constrain the lithospheric structure of the Yilgarn craton [2, 3]. In this study, we integrate Hf isotopes of zircon, together with bulk-rock Nd isotopes to constrain the lithospheric structure of NE Fennoscandia and the potential for different types of mineral systems.

Fig. 1 Geological map showing the distribution of Archean blocks in the Karelian Craton based on the geology map database of GTK. The hidden boundary between the Svecofennian orogenic belt and the Karelian craton is based on Nd isotope mapping of [4].

Archean geology and metallogeny in the Karelia geological province

Fennoscandia is divided into the Norrbotten, Murmansk, Kola, Belomorian and Karelia Provinces [5]. The Karelia province has been subdivided based on lithology, structures and ages into three sub-provinces: Western Karelia, Central Karelia and Vodlozero [1]. The study area is within the Western Karelia province located within Finland. The Karelia Province consists mainly of Tonalite-trondhjemite-granodiorite series rocks (TTGs) (about 80%), supracrustal rocks in greenstone belts, sedimentary gneisses, and migmatitic amphibolites forming enclaves in gneissic granitoids [6]. Based on field and petrographic characteristics, major and trace element compositions, and age, Archean granitoids in the Karelia Province can be divided into four main groups namely: tonalite-trondhjemite-granodiorite (TTG), sanukitoid, quartz diorite-quartz monzodiorite (QQ), and granodiorite-granite-monzogranite (GGM) [6]. TTGs have been broadly divided into two major groups, those showing low contents of heavy rare earth elements (HREE) and those with high HREE [7]. HREE-depleted TTGs have been found to be more common in the Archean than in younger periods, and their origin seems to be linked to tectonic thickening and subduction of oceanic crust, followed by progressive metamorphism and partial melting of basaltic rocks in a subducted slab, producing TTG melts in equilibrium with anhydrous, eclogitic residues [8]. Slightly younger granodiorite-granite-monzogranite (GGM) rocks are considered to be partial melting products of TTG rocks. There are some occurrences of major ore mineralization in the Western Karelia Block, including: komatiite-related Ni-Cu in Archean greenstone belts in northern and eastern Finland [5], orogenic gold deposits in Archean greenstone belts and 2.45 Ga PGE enriched layered intrusions at the boundary between Archean and Paleoproterozoic supracrustal belts, and felsic volcanic rock-related Ag-Pb-Zn deposits in greenstone belts, and the Siilinjärvi carbonatite-hosted apatite deposit [9].

Samples and methodology

Previous studies have determined ages and bulk-rock Sm-Nd isotope compositions of different types of Archean granitoids from the Karelian craton (e.g., [10]), providing a basis for this study. Samples covering different blocks of the Western Karelia province (e.g., Pudasjärvi, Taivalkoski, Iisalmi, Suomussalmi, Kuhmo) were selected for this study. As most granitoids were formed in the Neoarchean with ages ranging from about 2.7 to 2.8 Ga, these granitoids (TTG and granite) are selected for further study to map the spatial distribution of Hf-Nd isotopes across different Archean blocks.

Preliminary results and implication for mineralization

The Archean rocks have been dated using bulk-zircon U-Pb method [10]. This study applies Laser Ablation Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) for in-situ analyses of U-Pb isotopes of zircon grains. The results of more than 40 samples show that the in-situ ages agree well with the bulk-zircon U-Pb ages. Most samples show a positive correlation between ϵ_{Nd} and ϵ_{Hf} values indicating that in many cases, these two systems have remained closed systems. However, some samples record differences between the ϵ_{Nd} and ϵ_{Hf} values, showing slightly positive ϵ_{Nd} , but negative ϵ_{Hf} values. The Sm-Nd and Lu-Hf isotope systems from Western Karelia have been compared for about 20 samples, and there is generally positive correlation between Nd and Hf isotopes, but the crustal residence time of Hf in the zircons is systematically 300 Ma older than the bulk-rock Nd model ages [11]. Hence, it is recommended to combine bulk-rock data and mineral data due to multi-stage processes and potentially distinct sources for Hf in these granitoids [11].

Hf isotopes composition of the Taivalkoski block show a zoned pattern, with ϵ_{Hf} having systematically higher values in the marginal part compared with the central part. This feature is consistent with a similar pattern for ϵ_{Nd} values. The same feature has been observed in the Pudasjärvi block which shows the most negative ϵ_{Hf} (-7.4) and ϵ_{Nd} values (-5.5) in the center, and higher values outwards. Though the amount of Hf isotope data is limited, there are sufficient Nd isotope data. This is consistent with the occurrence of older inherited zircon populations in these granitoids. The Pudasjärvi block also hosts Finland's oldest rocks (3.5 Ga) in the Siurua trondhjemite

gneiss [12]. Hence, it is possible that there are Mesoarchean remains of micro-continents in these two blocks.

Granitoids from the Suomussalmi and Iisalmi blocks show negative ϵ_{Hf} and ϵ_{Nd} values, indicating an occurrence of older continental crust. On the other hand, granitoids from the Kuhmo block have only slightly negative ϵ_{Hf} and ϵ_{Nd} values, probably indicating the presence of limited (or no) Mesoarchean basement rocks. This is consistent with the observation that the 2.8 Ga greenstone belts show no signs of interaction with continental crustal materials [13]. A similar interpretation has been proposed for the Kostomuksha greenstone belt [14].

Fig. 2. Spatial distribution of ϵ_{Nd} (a) and ϵ_{Hf} (b) isotope values of 2.7-2.8 Ga granitoids in Western Karelina. Nd isotope data taken from [11].

The preliminary results indicate that in the Archean period, there were some Mesoarchean basement rocks in Pudasjärvi, Taivalkoski, and probably Suomussalmi and Iisalmi, but not in Kuhmo. The 2.45 Ga mafic layered intrusions clustered in a specific zone along the boundary between the Archean and Proterozoic, indicating a specific spatial controlling factor on the distribution of magmatism (Fig. 1). In the future, the Hf isotope database will be further expanded, and interpolation of Hf and Nd isotope will be conducted to constrain the crustal structure of western Karelina.

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